

HISTORICAL AND ARCHEOLOGICAL SCIENCES

ACTIVITIES OF MEDICAL RESEARCH CENTERTS IN AZERBAIJAN DURING THE SOVET PERIOD

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Abstract

During its stay in the Soviet Union, the Republic of Azerbaijan contributed to the Soviet healthcare system, and a number of important medical research centers were established in the republic. Among them, the research institutes "Virology, Microbiology and Hygiene", "occupational diseases", "experimental medicine", "blood transfusion", "protection of mother and child", "X-ray and Radiology" have done important work.

Since human health was one of the important principles of the state, the establishment and operation of medical research institutions in the republics, including Azerbaijan, were in the spotlight.

Keywords: Azerbaijani healthcare, research institutes, history of medicine, Soviet medical science, Soviet healthcare system.

Introductions: The history of Soviet medicine is a dynamically developing field of research, in which various approaches, scientific theories are reflected. An important place in this field of research is occupied by the history and activities of medical research institutions. During the period of the Soviet Union, the Republic of Azerbaijan also contributed to the Soviet health system, and a number of important medical research centers were established in the Republic.

Results and discussion: Consistent and systematic scientific research in the field of medicine in the Azerbaijan SSR began with the formation of the Faculty of Medicine at Baku University. Since the early 20s, the organization of research medical institutions on the basis of research clinics and laboratories began. The first medical research institution was the Institute of Virology, Microbiology and Hygiene. The Institute was established in 1922 on the initiative of the People's Commissariat of Health of the Azerbaijan SSR, the head of the Epidemiology Department of the People's Commissariat of Health, Dr. S. Slonevsky and the head of the Department of Bacteriology of the Medical Faculty of Baku State University P. Zdradovsky took an active part in the creation of the institute [14, p. 2]. The creation of this scientific institution was aimed at combating infectious diseases that are widespread among the population of the republic. In the 30s, a number of scientific and experimental institutions were established on the basis of this institute - the Sanitary and Epidemiological Institute, the Tropical Institute, the Anti-Plague Station, the Brucellosis station, the republican Sanitary and Epidemiological stations [12, p. 21]. In the spring of 1924, the staff of the Institute of Virology, Microbiology and Hygiene actively participated in the fight against the outbreak of rabies in Baku and Ganja [9, p. 6].

An important place in the scientific and experimental activities of the Institute was occupied by the fight against malaria, which is of national importance. In 1925, the Institute organized departments of diagnostics, bacteriology, tropical

diseases, vaccines, pathological anatomy and a chemical laboratory [13, p.76]. Since the mid-20s, the Institute has been conducting serious scientific research in the field of studying bacteriological infectious and parasitic diseases, in particular malaria. In 1925, the Department of Microbiology was organized here on the basis of the Microbiology laboratory [12, p. 22]. In 1922-1930, the study of brucellosis diseases began, which became widespread in the USSR, including in the republic. In the 30s, the Institute paid special attention to the study of acute infectious diseases, including their etymology, epidemiology, conducted effective scientific research in the fight against diseases such as dysentery, typhoid fever, scarlet fever [13, p.79].

During the Second World War, when the epidemiological environment was very tense, the staff of the Institute was involved in extensive work on the organization of sanitary and epidemiological measures. In 1945, a sanitary and hygienic station was organized on the basis of the sanitary and hygienic laboratory of the Institute, and later - the Republican Sanitary and Epidemiological Station. Special attention in the scientific and experimental activities of the Institute is occupied by the post-war years. During this period, the staff of the Institute, continuing their scientific research in the field of etymology, immunology and epidemiology of bacterial infectious diseases, achieved successful results in determining the main conjunctiva of viral and bacterial infectious diseases in the republic. A number of inventions and innovation proposals were successfully tested by scientists of the Institute. The research of the Virology Laboratory, established in 1952, was highly appreciated by the Leningrad Institute of Embryology and Microbiology [12, p.14]. In the second half of the 1950s, a broad study of polio began at the Institute, while scientific research continued in the field of studying chickenpox and viral hepatitis [12, p.22-24]. Since the 50s, this institute has also conducted research on toxoplasmosis [12, p.14].

In 1924-1925, the Institute for the Study of Occupational Diseases began its activity in Baku. The staff studied the sanitary conditions of workers in the oil industry, the toxicological properties of a number of oil products. The Institute's doctors laid the foundations of the science of occupational hygiene and occupational diseases in the republic. At the courses and seminars, reports and consultations on various issues of occupational hygiene and pathology were heard, and the research of the institute's employees was published in scientific papers. In the 30s, the institute was reorganized and divided into 2 scientific and experimental institutions: the Republican Stationary Station and the polyclinic of labor expertise. However, it should be noted that these enterprises, which operated until the end of the 50s, did not fully meet the requirements of that time [1, p.34].

The rapid development of the oil, petrochemical, chemical and other industries in the republic required the creation of a new research center that will deal with the problems of working conditions and occupational pathology. It was in this connection that the country's leadership decided in November 1960 to organize the Institute of Occupational Hygiene and Occupational Diseases under the Ministry of Health of the Azerbaijan SSR. The material and technical base of the Institute has been strengthened and equipped with modern equipment. At the end of the 60s, 83 employees worked in 3 departments of the Institute (occupational hygiene, occupational diseases and organizational and methodological department), of which 32 were medical researchers [15, p. 9]. At that time, the Department of Occupational Pathology of the Institute had inpatient, clinical diagnostic and biological chemical laboratories, functional diagnostic, physiotherapy and X-ray rooms. The Institute provided scientific and practical assistance to industrial enterprises, agricultural workers and health authorities, employees organized conferences, seminars in cities and districts of the republic, gave advice on protection from toxic chemicals.

Epidemic outbreaks of malaria were widespread in Azerbaijan, and tropical malaria was much more widespread. A systematic and consistent fight against this disease was required. As a result of studies conducted in the mid-20s on cotton and rice plantations of the Azerbaijan SSR, it was found that malaria is widespread in more than 16 administrative districts. For the first time since 1925-1926, serious measures were taken to combat malaria, malaria control stations were organized in Baku and district centers [11, p.5]. In order to take effective measures against this disease, as well as to combat parasitic diseases, the Azerbaijan Scientific Research Tropical Institute was organized in 1931. In order to take effective measures against this disease, as well as to combat parasitic diseases, the Azerbaijan Scientific Research Tropical Institute was organized in 1931 [11, p.5- 6]. The main task of the Institute's staff was to study the geographical areas of malaria patients, the fight against parasitic diseases and the adoption of various preventive measures. In 1940, there were 110 malaria control points in the republic [4, p.9].

Since 1945, courses on parasitic diseases have been organized at the Institute. In 1945-1958, 714 doctors, more than 1,000 laboratory assistants and other specialists were trained at the Institute [11, p.10-11]. As a result of studying the parasites that cause malaria, which killed thousands of people every year, it was possible to partially eradicate this disease in the 60s, while a complete victory over the disease was achieved through the use of green oil obtained from oil refining [16, p.48-54].

In 1947, on the initiative of the outstanding surgeon M.Topchubashev, the Institute of Experimental Medicine was established in the Azerbaijan SSR. The Institute has played an important role in the detailed study of a number of pathologies in the republic. In the 60-70s, the institute turned into a center for surgery of blood vessels, heart, lungs, endocrine glands, digestive organs. *Bəhs edilən dövrədə institutun şöbələrində və laboratoriyalarında ürək-damar xəstəliklərinin müalicəsi və profilaktikasına dair məsələlər üzrə tədqiqatlar aparılmışdı* [16, p.49]. In 1982, with the consent of the Ministry of Health of the Azerbaijan SSR, research work on the problems of surgical gastroenterology began at the Institute. Since 1993, a purulent-septic department has been established at the Institute, and conducting research on this topic was important [6, p. 9-10].

In order to carry out preventive measures and treatment of tuberculosis, a tuberculosis dispensary was opened in Baku in 1923. In 1925, tuberculosis dispensaries began functioning in Ganja, in 1926 in Sheki, and in subsequent years such dispensaries were opened in other cities of Azerbaijan. Dispensaries identified patients among the population, carried out sanitary and educational work, carried out preventive measures against tuberculosis [5, p. 6-9].

The Tuberculosis Research Institute conducted research on such problems as "The clinical course of tuberculosis in wartime", "The prevalence of tuberculosis among military personnel", "Pathomorphological features of tuberculosis in wartime". Based on the research of professors P.Blishchenko, G.Salimkhanov, V. Abdullayev, new methods of treatment began to be introduced at the Tuberculosis Institute. At that time, children born in the republic were given mass vaccinations against tuberculosis, sanitary and educational work was carried out among the population. 1955 can be considered a new stage in the development of phthisis surgery. At that time, the Tuberculosis Institute, Tuberculosis Hospital No. 4, dispensaries No. 1 and 3, as well as the Myasnikov Sanatorium regularly performed surgical operations in the field of lung diseases. In the 50s, new methods were used to identify tuberculosis patients, and significant progress was made in this area.

In the 60s, the study of tuberculosis continued in the Azerbaijan SSR, a number of statistical data were collected and published. During this period, Prof. under the guidance of Professor P. Blazhenkova studied the effect of naphthalene on tuberculosis infection, tuberculosis of bones, joints, lymph glands. In 1960, 128 tuberculosis institutions operated in the republic, including 5 tuberculosis hospitals, 44 dispensaries, 54

polyclinics, 25 sanatoriums. In 1960, 4677 patients were treated in 128 medical institutions fighting tuberculosis in the republic [5, p.4-5].

In 1931, the Red Crescent Society of the Azerbaijan SSR, considering the extremely important importance of blood transfusion in the sanitary protection of the population, organized a blood transfusion point at the Semashko Hospital in Baku [8, p. 24]. It was an important event in the medical life of the republic in the 30s. In the first period, the activity of this department was not active, very few doctors were engaged in blood transfusion. They went to medical institutions of the republic, helped the seriously ill. In 1943, the Azerbaijani Experimental Station was reorganized into the Republican Research Institute of Blood Transfusion and the Institute of Emergency Surgery. The Institute has started mass collection of blood for the front, conducting extensive agitation and propaganda work among the population, training donor personnel [10, p. 84-91].

After the Second World War, the Institute of Blood Transfusion began training personnel to manage stations in Ganja and Khankendi, as well as new stations organized in 15 district centers of the republic. In 1951-1955. The Institute provided advanced training and specialization of 41 medical workers with higher education and 187 with secondary education for transfusion institutions of the republic. The application of the method of preserving the mass of leukocytes by the Azerbaijan Scientific Research Institute of Blood Transfusion in 1955 gave a positive result [10, p. 89].

An important place in the organization and development of radiological science in the Azerbaijan SSR is occupied by the establishment of the Scientific Research Institute of Radiology in 1941. This was extremely important for the diagnosis and treatment of a number of diseases. From the very beginning of its activity, the Institute began to direct the scientific and medical work carried out in the republic in the field of radiology, and then oncology. An important role in the training of personnel in the field of radiology in the Azerbaijan SSR was played by the Azerbaijan Medical Institute, as well as the Azerbaijan Institute of Advanced Training of Doctors (Departments of Radiology and Medical Radiology [17, 9-11]. Since the 50s, the Institute has conducted research in the field of diagnosis and treatment of diseases of the gastrointestinal tract, cancer, malignant tumors of the female genital organs and mammary glands [17, p. 10]. Since February 1988, the Institute has been called the Republican Cancer Research Center.

In 1946, the Institute of Eye Diseases was organized on the basis of the Baku Eye Clinical Hospital with 1204 beds. The Institute has led scientific and experimental work in the field of combating the eye disease trachoma, has achieved great success in this field. The Institute, consisting of therapeutic, surgical and trachomatous departments, operated clinical diagnostic, bacteriological and pathomorphological laboratories.

Scientists of the Institute developed and put into practice a new method of functional mobility of the retina in the 60s, research was also conducted on new

methods that determine the effectiveness of treatment of vascular diseases of the eye [3, p.36]. The pathogenetic mechanisms of various forms of glaucoma were studied using electron microscopy, and herbal antibiotics were used to treat viral eye diseases. The staff of the Institute in the 1960s-1980s did a lot of work in the field of the introduction of scientific, methodological and experimental measures to combat trachoma.

Employees of the Institute have repeatedly gone on business trips to areas where trachoma is widespread. Treatment of patients, carrying out extensive sanitary-educational and preventive work gave a positive result. As a result of the practical work done in 1966, trachoma in the Azerbaijan SSR was completely eliminated [3, p. 36].

The Research Institute for Maternal and Infant Health began its activities in 1927, with the aim of solving theoretical and practical issues in the field of pediatrics and obstetrics-gynecology, combating maternal and child mortality, mass epidemics of childhood infections. Its organizer and first director was a pediatrician-doctor Evsei Gindes were [18, p. 83]. The Institute conducted research in the field of gynecology, physiology and pathology of the child's body, trained medical personnel. The Institute paid serious attention to sanitary and educational work among the population, medical personnel sent to the regions provided medical assistance to mothers and children [7, p. 5].

In this institute, which is a scientific and methodological center for the protection of motherhood and childhood, an important place was occupied by the fight against tuberculosis, fever (malaria), infectious diseases, pneumonia, pregnancy pathology, gynecological and other diseases..Since the 50s, the institute's staff began to deal with issues such as active vaccination immunity against blood diseases, intestinal infections [8, p. 85].

An important event in the health care of the Soviet Union was the opening in November 1934 of the Institute of Balneophysiology in Baku- a scientific and medical center. The Research Institute of Balneology and Physiotherapy, which began its activity in Azerbaijan in 1935, conducted serious research in the field of studying the therapeutic composition of naphthalan oil, mineral water sources in the early years [14, p. 4-10]. The scientists of the Institute conducted hydrogeological surveys in the field of detecting mineral water sources on the territory of the republic, identified new reserves of mineral water. The staff of the Research Institute of Cardiology, which began its activity in the early 1980s, studied new methods of prevention, diagnosis and treatment of diseases of the cardiovascular system.

Conclusions: The healthcare system in the USSR can be considered one of the important achievements of the Soviet people. Health protection issues were determined and implemented by the State. Insurance of employees of enterprises, along with an 8-hour working day, as well as sanitary supervision were important issues. Based on the principles of the Soviet health care system, there were a number of important issues, such

as free medical care for the population, professionalism, preventive orientation, protection of motherhood and childhood, sanitary and epidemiological services. From the first years of Soviet power, the health of workers was declared one of the most important principles of the state, in connection with which a network of medical research institutions was gradually created in the republics, including Azerbaijan, along with hospitals, polyclinics. It cannot be denied that the medical research centers of the present independent Republic of Azerbaijan developed and improved precisely on the basis of research institutions of the Soviet period.

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